

DAMAGE ACCUMULATION AND FRACTURE IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the effects of particle size and distribution on damage behaviour in particle reinforced metal matrix composites (PRMMCs) under different loading conditions. Two types of PRMMCs were studied: 1) molten metal processed and squeeze cast aluminum A356 + 15 μm diameter SiC, and 2) solid state powder processed and extruded commercial purity Al + 0.8, 3, or 12 μm SiC.

Three types of damage behaviour were observed: 1) Tensile loading - large, clustered particles. Damage is a combination of particle cracking and interface decohesion, and is concentrated in particle clusters. 2) Tensile loading - small, uniformly distributed particles. Particle cracking is suppressed, and fracture occurs by growth and coalescence of voids originating at particle interfaces. 3) Compression - large, uniformly distributed particles. Interface decohesion occurs due to tensile stresses which result from non-homogeneous flow of the matrix around the particles.

KEYWORDS: particle-reinforced MMCs, particle cracking, decohesion, damage, fracture

INTRODUCTION

The micromechanism of fracture in particulate reinforced metal matrix composites (PRMMCs) is a "locally ductile" process whereby the ductile fracture mechanism of void nucleation and growth occurs over a small fraction of the stressed volume and the macroscopic ductility is low.

Hence, ductile fracture models which were developed for materials containing low volume fractions ($< 1\%$) of uniformly dispersed particles [1,2] do not accurately predict the observed effects of particle volume fraction on fracture ductility or fracture toughness in PRMMCs [3]. In PRMMCs, the fracture process is a continuous nucleation and growth of voids (damage) with increasing strain until a critical damage condition for fracture is reached. The critical level of accumulated damage is 2 - 5 %, whether measured by an averaged property (eg., elastic modulus [4]) or by a microscopic measurement (eg., % damaged particles [5]). Most studies of the fracture behaviour of PRMMCs have been for particle sizes of 10 μm or larger, where particle cracking is the dominant damage mechanism [6,7]. In molten metal processed PRMMCs, the particle distribution is non-uniform (clustered), and damage is concentrated in the particle clusters [4,5]. The current models for void nucleation and growth and the prediction of fracture ductility in PRMMCs have been recently reviewed [8].

The objective of the present study was to determine the effects of particle size and distribution on damage behaviour in PRMMCs under different loading conditions. In particular, damage mechanisms were determined for material containing uniformly distributed particles $< 1 \mu\text{m}$ diameter, and compared with previous results for clustered distributions of larger particles.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two types of PRMMCs were studied. The first type was molten metal processed and squeeze cast aluminum A356 matrix alloy (Al-7Si-0.35Mg) reinforced with $15 \mu\text{m}$ diameter SiC particulate. Processing details are given elsewhere [5]. The second type of PRMMC studied was solid state powder processed commercial purity aluminum matrix (Al-0.26 Fe-0.18 Si) reinforced with 10 vol.% of SiC particulate, either $0.8 \mu\text{m}$, $3 \mu\text{m}$ or $12 \mu\text{m}$ diameter. $6.3 \mu\text{m}$ Al powder was mixed with the SiC, compacted and hot extruded at 500°C to 6.3 mm diameter rod with an extrusion ratio of $\sim 15:1$. This material was supplied by Risø National Laboratory, Denmark.

Particle distributions were characterized by optical metallography and image analysis. The mean values of volume fraction (V_f) and particle diameter (d) are given in Table 1. It was obvious from optical metallography (Fig. 1) that the particle distribution was non-uniform ('clustered') in the molten metal processed/squeeze cast material, and much more uniform in the powder processed/extruded material, especially for the smaller particle sizes.

Table 1: Characterization of MMC Materials

Material	V_f (%)	d (μm)	σ_y (MPa)	ϵ_f (%)
molten metal processed/squeeze cast A356-SiC	14.1 ± 1.9	15.0 ± 5.5	198	3.3
powder processed/extruded Al-SiC ($12 \mu\text{m}$)	11.2	10.1 ± 5.0	141	29
powder processed/extruded Al-SiC ($0.8 \mu\text{m}$)	10.7	0.8 ± 1.1	166	23

V_f = volume fraction of particulate
 σ_y = tensile yield stress

d = mean particle diameter
 ϵ_f = true fracture stress

*Fig. 1: Particle Distributions a) Molten Metal Processed/Squeeze Cast (15 μm)
b) Powder Processed/Extruded (0.8 μm)*

Fracture Tests and Characterization of Damage

Tensile tests were carried out on all materials at a crosshead speed of 0.005 mm/s, and fracture surfaces were examined by SEM. The sample dimensions were 4 mm diameter x 14 mm gauge length. Tensile yield stresses and fracture strains are reported in Table 1.

Four-point bend tests of double-notch samples were also carried out on the molten-metal processed/squeeze cast materials. This allowed the nature and extent of pre-fracture damage to be determined from examination of the microstructure at the uncracked notch. A complete description of this technique is given elsewhere [5].

Direct observations of damage initiation in the 3 μm powder-processed/extruded material were made by performing notched tensile tests *in-situ* in an environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM). The sample dimensions were 5.4 mm² cross-section, 25 mm length, with a 3.5 mm notch in the centre of the gauge length. The microscope was focussed to observe initiation and development of damage at the notch tip.

Machining Tests and Characterization of Damage

Machining tests were carried out by orthogonal cutting the ends of cylinders of the MMC samples. The cylinders were 5.0 mm diameter x 1.25 mm wall thickness. The cutting tool was a polycrystalline diamond (PCD) tool bit having a rake face angle of 7° and a tool nose radius of 0.8 mm. In orthogonal cutting, both the (single) cutting edge and the feed direction are perpendicular to the direction of workpiece (rotational) velocity. The depth of cut was held constant at 1.25 mm, feed rate was either 0.05 or 0.20 mm/rotation, and the rotational speed was either 500 rpm or 1500 rpm.

Machined chips were collected and mounted to examine either the chip surface or cross section by optical metallography and SEM. “Quick-stop” samples were obtained by stopping the lathe suddenly, which captured the chip on the workpiece. Material was cut from the workpiece with the chip attached so that the complete deformation zone could be studied. The flow pattern of the material in the deformation zone was enhanced by etching the mounted and polished samples in 0.5 % HF for approximately 30 s.

RESULTS

Damage in Molten Metal Processed MMCs Containing 15 μm Particles

The development of damage prior to fracture was studied by examining the region near the tip of the uncracked notch in the double-notched 4-point bend samples. Fig. 2 shows that damage was not uniformly distributed, rather it developed preferentially at clusters of particles. The damage was a combination of particle cracking and interface decohesion, and approximately 5 % of particles were damaged at the point of fracture initiation. Examination of the region near the cracked notch indicated that the crack path linked damage clusters. SEM of fracture surfaces revealed evidence of particle cracking, interface decohesion, small dimples associated with Si needles and localized areas of matrix rupture. Measurements of area fraction of SiC particles (cracked and decohered) on the fracture surface gave values of 22-30% for all samples, again indicating that fracture propagated through the high V_f regions of the particle clusters.

*Fig. 2: Damage at Uncracked Notch in 4-Pt. Bend Test
(Molten Metal Processed/Squeeze Cast (15 μm))*

Damage in Powder Processed MMCs Containing 0.8 μm , 3 μm and 12 μm Particles

In comparison with the squeeze-cast A356-SiC material, the extruded Al-SiC had lower yield strength and much higher fracture strain (Table 1). *In-situ* ESEM tests of material containing 3 μm particles showed that the damage initiation was in the form of particle-matrix decohesion, with minimal particle cracking. After void nucleation at interfaces, damage progressed by void growth and coalescence in the matrix (Fig. 3). The damage and fracture characteristics were strongly dependent on particle size. For the 12 μm particles, the dominant damage mechanism was particle cracking. Fracture surfaces of this material revealed a combination of cracked particles and ductile failure in the matrix with ~ 1 μm dimples (Fig. 4a). There was no particle cracking in the MMCs containing 0.8 μm particles and the only damage associated with the particles was interface decohesion. Fracture surfaces

of this material showed completely ductile failure with $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ dimples (Fig. 4b). A few of the dimples contained visible particles. There were also some secondary dimples $\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter (Fig. 4b @ arrow).

Fig. 3: Damage Observed During In-Situ ESEM Test (Powder Processed/Extruded ($3 \mu\text{m}$))

*Fig. 4: Fracture Surfaces in Tensile Tests (Powder Processed/Extruded)
a) $12 \mu\text{m}$ b) $0.8 \mu\text{m}$*

Damage During Machining of Powder Processed MMCs

In all cases, the chips produced were quasi-continuous and had a serrated edge, indicating segmented chip formation [9]. Again, there was a distinct effect of particle size on damage mechanism. For the samples containing $12 \mu\text{m}$ particles, there was clear evidence of interface decohesion and void growth in the machined chips (Fig. 5a). Increasing the rotational speed increased the strain rate and resulted in a corresponding increase in damage. In contrast, there was no evidence of damage in the machined chips of the $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ MMC (Fig. 5b). A quick-stop section of the $12 \mu\text{m}$ material revealing the flow pattern in the deformation zone is shown in Fig. 5c. The non-homogeneous flow of the matrix around the particles is evident and voids which have formed at particle interfaces are indicated by arrows. Quick-stop sections of the $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ MMCs showed no evidence of non-homogeneous flow around particles and no void formation in the deformation zone. The distinctly different damage behaviour for the 2

particle sizes was reflected in the ease of chip fracture. The 0.8 μm MMC produced long chips, whereas the 12 μm MMC fractured more frequently and produced shorter chips.

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5: Damage During Orthogonal Machining (Powder Processed/Extruded)
a) Chip Cross-Section (12 μm) *b) Chip Cross-Section (0.8 μm)*
c) Quick-Stop Sample Showing Deformation Zone (12 μm)

DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate the effects of particle size and distribution on the pre-fracture damage mechanisms. The degree of damage is also a function of stress state, and differs widely for the predominantly tensile stress state in bend- and tensile tests, in contrast with machining where there is a combination of compression and shear stresses. Three different combinations of loading condition and particle distribution are considered, and damage models are described for each: i) tensile loading - large, clustered particles, ii) tensile loading - small, uniformly distributed particles, iii) compression - large, uniformly distributed particles. Schematic diagrams for each case are shown in Fig. 6.

Tensile Loading - Large, Clustered Particles

The damage is concentrated in particle clusters (Figs. 2 and 6a). Cracking and interface decohesion of individual particles as well as matrix failure are observed in the damage clusters. The voids which develop in the particle clusters do not grow extensively in the tensile direction. This is consistent with constraint of plastic flow in the matrix leading to triaxial stress intensification. The maximum tensile stress can be estimated by considering the deformation of a volume of matrix between particles to be equivalent to uniaxial deformation between elastic platens with sticking friction at the interface [4]. In a typical particle cluster, the dimensions of the constrained matrix are approximately $1\text{-}2\ \mu\text{m} \times 15\ \mu\text{m}$, which gives $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 1600 - 3000\ \text{MPa}$ [5]. Thus, high tensile stresses in the particle clusters lead to damage by particle cracking, as well as interface decohesion.

The critical condition for fracture would be determined by the size and spacing of the damage clusters. It has been shown that the fracture toughness (K_{IC}) depends strongly on the degree of particle clustering [5].

Tensile Loading - Small, Uniformly Distributed Particles

For particle diameters $3\ \mu\text{m}$ or less, there is no particle cracking and the sole damage mechanism is particle-matrix interface decohesion (Figs. 3 and 6b). There are 2 reasons why the particle fracture stress is not reached. With uniformly distributed particles, there is no stress intensification by plastic constraint. Secondly, the fracture stress of SiC increases with decreasing particle diameter, because the probable length of an intrinsic flaw is proportional to particle diameter [7]. Although the damage is relatively uniformly distributed, Fig. 3 indicates that the voids which form at particle interfaces grow primarily in the lateral direction perpendicular to the tensile axis.

The fracture condition is that for void coalescence, and the resulting fracture surfaces show dimples predominantly $1\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, which is comparable to the particle spacing. The $0.1\ \mu\text{m}$ secondary dimples could form at small Al_2O_3 particles which originate with the powder processing. Thus, it is expected that the fracture strain will vary with mean particle spacing, as shown by the data in Table 1.

Compression - Large, Uniformly Distributed Particles

Ideally, orthogonal cutting occurs by a pure shear deformation at the plane which separates the workpiece from the chip. In reality, deformation occurs over a significant volume of the workpiece material, under a combination of compressive and shear stresses. Deformation

begins well ahead of the tool bit, as seen in Fig.5c. The workpiece material is initially compressed in the direction perpendicular to the tool rake face, then deformed by shear into the chip. The observations on damage in the deformation zone can be explained by considering simple compressive loading (Fig. 6c). With large particles (Fig. 5a), tensile stresses develop in the matrix normal to the compression axis due to non-homogeneous flow of the matrix, leading to interface decohesion. There is no particle cracking because the particles are in compression. The degree of non-homogeneous flow, and the magnitude of the tensile stresses decrease with decreasing particle diameter [10]. This explains the absence of damage in the MMCs containing $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$ particles (Fig.5b)

Fracture of chips takes place when a critical damage level is reached and void coalescence occurs. Since the damage rate is higher at the larger particle size, fracture is frequent and the mean chip length is small. Conversely, the damage rate is low for small particle size and the chips are much longer.

Fig. 6: Damage Models for Different Particle Distributions and Load Geometries
a) Tensile - Clustered, Large Particles b) Tensile - Small Particles
c) Machining - Large Particles
(dashed arrows indicate direction of void growth)

CONCLUSIONS

The following characteristics of damage accumulation and fracture in PRMMCs have been described:

1. In MMCs containing large ($> 10\ \mu\text{m}$), clustered particles (such as produced by molten metal processing), local tensile stresses in the particle clusters are high leading to preferential damage initiation in those regions. Under these conditions, damage is a combination of particle cracking and interface decohesion. Fracture toughness varies inversely with the degree of particle clustering.
2. Particle cracking is suppressed in MMCs containing small ($< 3\ \mu\text{m}$), uniformly distributed particles (such as produced by powder processing). Fracture occurs by growth and coalescence of voids originating at particle interfaces, and fracture ductility varies inversely with mean particle spacing.

3. When deformed in compression (e.g., machining), interface decohesion occurs due to tensile stresses in the matrix which result from non-homogeneous flow of the matrix around the particles. With decreasing particle diameter, the damage rate decreases and chip formation becomes more difficult.

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